

Detection of Diabetic Retinopathy Using Neural Network

Aryan Kokane¹, Gourhari Sharma¹, Akash Raina¹, Shubham Narole¹, Prof. Pramila M. Chawan²

¹B. Tech Student, Dept. of Computer Engineering and IT, VJTI College, Mumbai, Maharashtra, India

²Associate Professor, Dept. of Computer Engineering and IT, VJTI College, Mumbai, Maharashtra, India

Abstract- Diabetic Retinopathy (DR) is a common eye disease which is contracted by diabetic people which may cause problems to the retina of the eye resulting in total or partial blindness. Therefore it is vital to identify diabetic retinopathy in the early stages. This paper aims to detect the diabetic retinopathy using neural networks and to give a decision about the presence of diabetic retinopathy. It will give us accuracy of our model.

Key Words: Diabetic Retinopathy, Opencv, convolutional layer, fully connected layer, convolutional neural network, feature extraction

1. INTRODUCTION

Diabetic Retinopathy (DR) can cause loss of vision because the blood vessels within the retina leak fluid or hemorrhage (bleed), which may lead to a blurred or impaired vision. Diabetic retinopathy is diagnosed by recognizing anomalies on retinal images taken by funduscopy. Because fundoscopic images are the primary method for diagnosis, going through them manually and analyzing those images are often time-consuming and unreliable, as the ability of detecting abnormalities varies. In this paper we aim to provide an automated, appropriate and sophisticated approach using convolution neural networks so that DR can be detected easily and the consequences can be minimized. This is an ongoing challenge problem on Kaggle which tries to develop a model for DR detection. Dataset is taken from the challenge-data part.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Harry Pratt et al. in this paper [1], proposed a convolutional neural network approach to diagnosing and classifying Diabetic Retinopathy from digital fundus images. They develop a network with CNN architecture and data augmentation which can identify the features involved in the classification task such as micro-aneurysms, exudate and haemorrhages on the retina. They train this network using a high-end graphics processor unit (GPU) on the publicly available Kaggle dataset and show good results, especially for a high-level classification task. On the data set of 80,000 images used their proposed CNN achieves a specificity of 95% and an accuracy of 75% on 5,000 validation images.

Athira et al. [2] proposed a R-CNN(Regional Convolutional Neural Network) to detect DR from digital fundus images. They implemented an approach where the image was segmented and only the regions of interest were taken for further processing. 10 layers were used for R-CNN, and trained on 130 fundus images and tested on 110 images. An accuracy of about 75.8% is obtained for R-CNN.

E. V. Carrera et al. in this paper [3] proposes a computer assisted diagnosis based on the digital processing of retinal image. This was performed on the Messidor dataset which consists of 1200 eye fundus color numerical images of the posterior pole captured by a special camera whose description is provided in their thesis. The objective of this was to detect any grade of DRNP. For that, they used 301 retinal images, 152 with grade 0 and 149 with grade 3. They trained a SVM classifier with all the features of these images and then tested it through a 10-fold cross-validation process. They achieved a sensitivity of 94.6% and a predictive capacity value of 93.8%.

Wong Li Yun et al. [4] used the K-means algorithm to extract features and Self-Organizing Map (SOM) classifier. The steps involved which are involved: Data Acquisition, K-means clustering for Feature Extraction and Self Organising Map for Classification. The classifier separates the cluster centroids of the normal class and the DR class. This model is only able to classify whether or not DR is present.

Salman Sayed et al. [5] used two models selected for detection of DR are Probabilistic Neural Network (PNN) and Support vector machines (SVM) and their results were analysed and compared. The DR has been classified into two categories NPDR and PDR with a sensitivity of 81.42% and specificity of 100%.

3. PROPOSED SYSTEM

3.1 PROBLEM STATEMENT

“To detect diabetic retinopathy using neural network”

3.2 DATASET DESCRIPTION

For this project, we have taken the dataset from Kaggle [6]. In this dataset we are provided with a large set of high-resolution retina images taken under a variety of imaging conditions. A left eye image and right eye is provided for every subject and images are labeled with a subject id as well as if they are left or right.

Diabetic retinopathy in each image is labeled on a scale of 0 to 4, according to the following scale:

- 0 - No DR
- 1 - Mild
- 2 - Moderate
- 3 - Severe
- 4 - Proliferative DR

Some images appear to one as they would see the retina through an anatomy in which the macula is on the left, optic nerve on the right for the right eye while others images appear as one would see through a microscope lens i.e. inverted. Like any real-world dataset, this dataset also contains noise in both the images and labels.

3.3 DATA PREPROCESSING

The dataset has images of patients of different age groups and extremely varied levels of brightness in the fundus photography. The pixel intensity values of different regions of the images are affected. To rectify this, colour normalisation is implemented. The images are high resolution so they have a large memory size. As the size is too large, RGB images are converted into gray scale images. The dataset was resized to 200x200 pixels which retained the important features. As our model is a Convolutional Neural Network, not much preprocessing is required.

Fig - 1: Sample image after preprocessing

3.4 MODEL DESCRIPTION

A CNN model is used as proposed for the detection which is done by supervised learning by analyzing the features of training data [7]. We are proposing Convolutional Neural Network as it is suitable for computer vision because it consists of filters which lowers the necessary parameter storing which in turn reduces memory usage. It then uses pooling functions to compress the input image thus reducing memory. Also it is less complex because filters operate on limited size of input.

It is an adaptation of a multilayer perceptron and needs only less pre-processing techniques. The model comprises a number of convolutional layers, pooling layers, fully connected layers and Softmax. Convolutional layer is basically used for feature extraction followed by a ReLU activation function. The first convolutional layer concentrates on the low-level features, and with furthermore layers, the architecture adapts to the high-level features. The extracted features can be reduced in dimension as compared to the input, or the other in which the dimensionality is either increased or remains the same. This is done by applying valid padding or same padding. Max pooling is applied which helps reduce overfitting and reducing parameters. Max Pooling returns the maximum value from the region of the image covered by the kernel. Then, we are going to flatten the final output, i.e. to convert the multidimensional vector to a 1-dimensional vector, for classification purposes. Dropout layer is used near fully connected layer to prevent over creation of extra parameters. Some of the Dense layers have ReLU activation, or sigmoid activation or Softmax for classification. Over a series of epochs, the model is able to distinguish between important and low-level features in images and then classify them.

- Batch size to train = 32
- Number of output classes = 5
- Number of convolutional filters to use = 32
- Size of pooling area for max pooling = 2
- Convolution kernel size = 3*3

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #	Connected to
input_1 (InputLayer)	(None, 200, 200, 1)	0	
conv2d_1 (Conv2D)	(None, 98, 98, 16)	416	input_1[0][0]
leaky_re_lu_1 (LeakyReLU)	(None, 98, 98, 16)	0	conv2d_1[0][0]
conv2d_2 (Conv2D)	(None, 98, 98, 16)	2320	leaky_re_lu_1[0][0]
conv2d_3 (Conv2D)	(None, 98, 98, 16)	6416	leaky_re_lu_1[0][0]
leaky_re_lu_2 (LeakyReLU)	(None, 98, 98, 16)	0	conv2d_2[0][0]
leaky_re_lu_3 (LeakyReLU)	(None, 98, 98, 16)	0	conv2d_3[0][0]
concatenate_1 (Concatenate)	(None, 98, 98, 32)	0	leaky_re_lu_2[0][0] leaky_re_lu_3[0][0]
conv2d_4 (Conv2D)	(None, 47, 47, 32)	25632	concatenate_1[0][0]
leaky_re_lu_4 (LeakyReLU)	(None, 47, 47, 32)	0	conv2d_4[0][0]
conv2d_5 (Conv2D)	(None, 47, 47, 32)	9248	leaky_re_lu_4[0][0]
conv2d_6 (Conv2D)	(None, 47, 47, 32)	25632	leaky_re_lu_4[0][0]
leaky_re_lu_5 (LeakyReLU)	(None, 47, 47, 32)	0	conv2d_5[0][0]
leaky_re_lu_6 (LeakyReLU)	(None, 47, 47, 32)	0	conv2d_6[0][0]
concatenate_2 (Concatenate)	(None, 47, 47, 64)	0	leaky_re_lu_5[0][0] leaky_re_lu_6[0][0]
conv2d_7 (Conv2D)	(None, 47, 47, 32)	2080	concatenate_2[0][0]
leaky_re_lu_7 (LeakyReLU)	(None, 47, 47, 32)	0	conv2d_7[0][0]
conv2d_8 (Conv2D)	(None, 47, 47, 32)	1056	leaky_re_lu_7[0][0]
conv2d_9 (Conv2D)	(None, 47, 47, 32)	9248	leaky_re_lu_7[0][0]
leaky_re_lu_8 (LeakyReLU)	(None, 47, 47, 32)	0	conv2d_8[0][0]
leaky_re_lu_9 (LeakyReLU)	(None, 47, 47, 32)	0	conv2d_9[0][0]
concatenate_3 (Concatenate)	(None, 47, 47, 64)	0	leaky_re_lu_8[0][0] leaky_re_lu_9[0][0]
conv2d_10 (Conv2D)	(None, 22, 22, 64)	102464	concatenate_3[0][0]
leaky_re_lu_10 (LeakyReLU)	(None, 22, 22, 64)	0	conv2d_10[0][0]
conv2d_11 (Conv2D)	(None, 22, 22, 64)	36928	leaky_re_lu_10[0][0]
conv2d_12 (Conv2D)	(None, 22, 22, 64)	102464	leaky_re_lu_10[0][0]
leaky_re_lu_11 (LeakyReLU)	(None, 22, 22, 64)	0	conv2d_11[0][0]
leaky_re_lu_12 (LeakyReLU)	(None, 22, 22, 64)	0	conv2d_12[0][0]
concatenate_4 (Concatenate)	(None, 22, 22, 128)	0	leaky_re_lu_11[0][0] leaky_re_lu_12[0][0]
conv2d_13 (Conv2D)	(None, 22, 22, 64)	8256	concatenate_4[0][0]
leaky_re_lu_13 (LeakyReLU)	(None, 22, 22, 64)	0	conv2d_13[0][0]
conv2d_14 (Conv2D)	(None, 22, 22, 64)	4160	leaky_re_lu_13[0][0]
conv2d_15 (Conv2D)	(None, 22, 22, 64)	36928	leaky_re_lu_13[0][0]
leaky_re_lu_14 (LeakyReLU)	(None, 22, 22, 64)	0	conv2d_14[0][0]
leaky_re_lu_15 (LeakyReLU)	(None, 22, 22, 64)	0	conv2d_15[0][0]
concatenate_5 (Concatenate)	(None, 22, 22, 128)	0	leaky_re_lu_14[0][0] leaky_re_lu_15[0][0]
conv2d_16 (Conv2D)	(None, 9, 9, 64)	204864	concatenate_5[0][0]
leaky_re_lu_16 (LeakyReLU)	(None, 9, 9, 64)	0	conv2d_16[0][0]
conv2d_17 (Conv2D)	(None, 9, 9, 64)	36928	leaky_re_lu_16[0][0]
conv2d_18 (Conv2D)	(None, 9, 9, 64)	102464	leaky_re_lu_16[0][0]
leaky_re_lu_17 (LeakyReLU)	(None, 9, 9, 64)	0	conv2d_17[0][0]
leaky_re_lu_18 (LeakyReLU)	(None, 9, 9, 64)	0	conv2d_18[0][0]
concatenate_6 (Concatenate)	(None, 9, 9, 128)	0	leaky_re_lu_17[0][0] leaky_re_lu_18[0][0]
conv2d_19 (Conv2D)	(None, 9, 9, 64)	8256	concatenate_6[0][0]
leaky_re_lu_19 (LeakyReLU)	(None, 9, 9, 64)	0	conv2d_19[0][0]
conv2d_20 (Conv2D)	(None, 9, 9, 64)	4160	leaky_re_lu_19[0][0]
conv2d_21 (Conv2D)	(None, 9, 9, 64)	36928	leaky_re_lu_19[0][0]
leaky_re_lu_20 (LeakyReLU)	(None, 9, 9, 64)	0	conv2d_20[0][0]
leaky_re_lu_21 (LeakyReLU)	(None, 9, 9, 64)	0	conv2d_21[0][0]
concatenate_7 (Concatenate)	(None, 9, 9, 128)	0	leaky_re_lu_20[0][0] leaky_re_lu_21[0][0]
conv2d_22 (Conv2D)	(None, 7, 7, 64)	73792	concatenate_7[0][0]
leaky_re_lu_22 (LeakyReLU)	(None, 7, 7, 64)	0	conv2d_22[0][0]
conv2d_23 (Conv2D)	(None, 5, 5, 32)	18464	leaky_re_lu_22[0][0]
max_pooling2d_1 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 2, 2, 32)	0	conv2d_23[0][0]
flatten_1 (Flatten)	(None, 128)	0	max_pooling2d_1[0][0]
dense_1 (Dense)	(None, 512)	66048	flatten_1[0][0]
dense_2 (Dense)	(None, 128)	65664	dense_1[0][0]
leaky_re_lu_23 (LeakyReLU)	(None, 128)	0	dense_2[0][0]
dropout_1 (Dropout)	(None, 128)	0	leaky_re_lu_23[0][0]
dense_3 (Dense)	(None, 5)	645	dropout_1[0][0]

Fig 2: Model Summary

Total params: 991,461
 Trainable params: 991,461
 Non-trainable params: 0

4. IMPLEMENTATION

The project is run on a system with Windows 10 with a configuration of Core™ i7 Processor Model and a NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1050 Graphics Controller. We have used python as our programming language throughout this project and performed it on Jupyter notebook. There are a number of libraries available in python which we have used such as: NumPy, Pandas, PIL, Keras.

NumPy : Used to read the dataset images as a NumPy array ndarray and the various image processing were performed using NumPy functions.

PIL : Used for opening, manipulating, and saving many different images present in our database.

Pandas : To read and convert csv files to pandas dataframe.

Keras : To build the neural network

As suggested by More, Nikhil T. et al. [8], the requirements that have been defined for the project influence the rate of success of the project.

5. RESULTS

We have gone for a 80:20 split, i.e 4000 training samples and 1000 test samples. Data augmentation is performed. An accuracy of 74.8% is achieved.

Fig. 3: Training and Validation accuracy over 50 epochs

6. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

As we can see from our results, it is quite encouraging with an accuracy of 74.8% and is comparable with other models out there. Future scope would be modifications such as increase size of test and training data set, or to use an improved algorithm to get clearer features or in place of direct image features try to use gradient of RGB layers

could improve efficiency and results. Acquiring acceptable accuracy can lead the people in early detection of retinopathy.

7. REFERENCES

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